

Manifestation Of Individual Creativity In Teaching Chemistry

Saidakhmedova Nurkhon Yusupovna
Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry
of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute,

Sodikov Murojon Usmonalievich
Senior teacher of the Department of Chemistry
of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute,

Kholmatov Abdukhamid Azamjonovich
Kokan is a student of DPI,

Abstract: The creative approach to the development of student cognitive activity is fully covered, with its practical significance interconnected.

Keywords — creative approach, the creator, creative, case, yeast, identify the problem.

INTRODUCTION.

Themes (motives) such as self-activation, self-creativity, self-knowledge and creativity are of great importance in the activity of a teacher. This gives an opportunity to form the creativity of the teacher.

The concept of "creativity" lexically (lat.) expresses the meanings of "creatio" - "creation", "creative" - creator, creator, and in essence it means "manifesting the ability of individual creativity".

Creativity is an individual's readiness to produce new ideas to the composition of talent as a descriptive and independent factor

incoming creative ability.

Creativity (E.P. Torrens):

- putting forward a problem or scientific hypothesis;
- hypothesis testing and modification;
- identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results;
- expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem

Important qualities reflected in the basis of creativity

An important condition for innovation is to create a new situation of communication.

Case 1. The baker mixes flour, water, salt and yeast into the dough for bread. Then the dough is placed in a container and left for a few hours for the fermentation process to take place. As a result of fermentation, chemical processes take place in the dough.

Picture 1

Questions:

Question 1: As a result of kneading the dough for bread, the dough rises. Why does the dough rise?

Question 2. A few hours after the bread dough has risen, the baker measures the dough and finds that the mass of the dough has decreased. Which two experiments should be compared to determine whether the decrease in dough mass is due to yeast?

3. What do you think?
4. How would you solve these problems?

Recommended resources for listeners:

Literature on biological chemistry.

Instructions for listeners:

1. Understand the essence of the case.
2. Determine the factors that serve to find a solution to the problem.
3. Among the identified factors, identify the factor (or two factors) most likely to contribute to the problem.
4. Try to justify the solution based on these factors.
5. Express your opinion.

Case resolution process:

1. Listeners discuss the essence of the case in a small group by getting to know it.
2. The listener, in cooperation with the members of the small group, determines the factors that prepare the ground for solving the problem.
3. The most important factors that make it possible to solve the problem are distinguished.
4. The members of the small group state the most important factors based on the general opinion.
5. The opinions of small groups are analyzed and a general conclusion is made[3].

Teacher's solution

1. In the dough, yeast (one-cell fungus) converts starch and sugar contained in flour into carbon monoxide and alcohol [1].

2. Due to the increase of dough, carbon monoxide and alcohol are released in large quantities. Knead the dough from time to time. The reason is that the fat and milk in the dough prevent the formation of gas. Then the dough will rise quickly. The dough becomes porous and the mass of the dough decreases.

The innovative activity of the teacher is aimed at changing the reality, identifying the solutions to its problems and methods. Changing the pattern of communication between a teacher and a student is one of the conditions of innovative activity [2]. New relationships should be free of elements such as demands and judgments, as in traditions. They should be built in the form of cooperation of equals, mutual management, mutual support. The most important feature of their relationship is the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student.

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